

Electric Dipole Moment of some Aliphatic Amines

A. N. SRIVASTAVA and P. R. TALESARA

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur.

Manuscript received 3 September 1973 ; accepted 5 February 1975

We have measured the dipole moment of n-amylamine, iso-amylamine and di-n-amylamine in benzene and dioxane at 30°. The experimental data have been employed to understand the accuracy in results reported earlier⁶. Our data in dioxane are new as no one appears to have determined them previously.

THE equations which have been in frequent use to evaluate the orientation polarisation and then to calculate the solution moment value are due to Hedestrand¹, Hoecker², Halverstadt and Kumler³, Lefevre and Vine⁴. These authors have obtained their results under a few assumptions.

Earlier we have shown that the equation due to Palit⁵ involving no assumption can give a better insight while evaluating the dipole moment value from orientation polarisation data. Consequently the purpose of the present work has been (i) to check and compare the dipole moment value of the said amines by the method due to Palit and (ii) also to understand the merits of Palit equation.

Experimental

The method and technique employed have been described elsewhere⁵. The experimental data have been shown in the following Tables.

TABLE 1—ISO-AMYL AMINE IN BENZENE

$\epsilon_1 = 2.2630$	$d_1 = 0.8681$	$n_1 = 1.4956$	
$w_2 \times 10^3$	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	n_{12}
11.09	2.2869	0.8664	1.4950
21.32	2.3080	0.8645	1.4935
32.53	2.3274	0.8630	1.4920
42.56	2.3502	0.8608	1.4910
51.59	2.3776	0.8597	1.4900
61.81	2.3936	0.8581	1.4890

Values of the constants in the equation of Palit.

$$\alpha_0 = 2.1428 \quad P_{2\mu} \text{ (orientation polarisation)} = 41.47 \text{ ml}$$

$$\beta_0 = -0.1666 \quad \mu = 1.43 \text{ D}$$

$$\nu_0 = -0.1083$$

Values of the constants in the equation of Halverstadt and Kumler

$$\alpha = 2.3882 \quad \epsilon_1 = 2.2618 \quad P_{200} = 70.88 \text{ ml}$$

$$\beta = 0.2440 \quad V_1 = 1.1522 \quad \mu = 1.44 \text{ D}$$

TABLE 2—DI (N)-AMYL AMINE IN BENZENE

$\epsilon_1 = 2.2630$	$d_1 = 0.8680$	$n_1 = 1.4952$	
$w_2 = 10^3$	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	n_{12}
39.03	2.2853	0.8628	1.4915
74.24	2.3018	0.8587	1.4880
92.09	2.3089	0.8564	1.4870
108.74	2.3248	0.8540	1.4850
124.63	2.3342	0.8526	1.4830
139.41	2.3419	0.8504	1.4820
158.69	2.3517	0.8483	1.4805

Values of the constants in the equation of Palit.

$$\alpha_0 = 0.5714 \quad P_{2\mu} \text{ (orientation polarisation)} = 26.59 \text{ ml}$$

$$\beta_0 = -0.1266 \quad \mu = 1.43 \text{ D}$$

$$\nu_0 = -0.0944$$

Values of the constants in the equation of Halverstadt and Kumler

$$\alpha = 1.0565 \quad \epsilon_1 = 2.2630 \quad P_{200} = 76.58 \text{ ml}$$

$$\beta = 0.3084 \quad V_1 = 1.1532 \quad \mu = 1.10 \text{ D}$$

TABLE 3—N-AMYL AMINE IN DIOXAN

f_2	0.0099	0.0192	0.0283	0.0372	0.0459	0.0547	0.0635	0.0715
V_{12}	0.9822	0.9853	0.9890	0.9922	0.9955	0.9991	1.0022	1.0051
ϵ_{12}	2.2315	2.2589	2.2829	2.3017	2.3211	2.3388	2.3605	2.3850

Values of the constants in the equation of Halverstadt and Kumler

$$\alpha = 2.3938 \quad \epsilon_1 = 2.2108 \quad P_{200} = 68.99 \text{ ml}$$

$$\beta = 0.3775 \quad V_1 = 0.9783 \quad \mu = 1.41 \text{ D}$$

TABLE 4—ISO-AMYL AMINE IN DIOXAN

f_2	0.0099	0.0198	0.0293	0.0388	0.0477	0.0568
V_{12}	0.9820	0.9860	0.9889	0.9930	0.9959	0.9996
ϵ_{12}	2.2287	2.2549	2.2755	2.3080	2.3274	2.3531

Values of the constants in the equation of Halverstadt and Kumler

$$\alpha = 2.6618 \quad \epsilon_1 = 2.2014 \quad P_{200} = 72.73 \text{ ml}$$

$$\beta = 0.3709 \quad V_1 = 0.9783 \quad \mu = 1.48 \text{ D}$$

TABLE 5—DI (N)-AMYL AMINE IN DIOXAN

f_2	0.0202	0.0374	0.0488	0.0586	0.0667	0.0760	0.0860
V_{12}	0.9913	1.0012	1.0078	1.0139	1.0183	1.0232	1.0281
ϵ_{12}	2.2365	2.2557	2.2601	2.2711	2.2782	2.2864	2.3045

Values of the constants in the equation of Halverstadt and Kumler

$$\alpha = 0.9581 \quad \epsilon_1 = 2.2160 \quad P_{200} = 72.60 \text{ ml}$$

$$\beta = 0.5574 \quad V_1 = 0.9802 \quad \mu = 1.01 \text{ D}$$

TABLE 6—APPARENT DIPOLE MOMENT VALUES OF AMINES IN DEBYE UNITS (μ S)

Name of the Solute	Benzene		Dioxan		
	by Present author Halverstadt and Kumler method	Palit method	by earlier worker ⁶	by Present author (Halverstadt and Kumler method)	by earlier worker ⁶
n-Amyl amine	1.47*	1.47	1.55	1.41	—
Iso-amyl amine	1.44	1.43	1.53	1.48	—
Di (n)-amyl amine	1.10	1.15	—	1.01	—

* This value is reported in our earlier paper in the Journal of Indian Chem. Soc., 1971, 48, 359.

Result and Discussion

The data in Table 6 demonstrate that the dipole moment values for n-amyl amine and Di (n)-amyl amine in benzene are greater than the corresponding values in dioxan. This fact is in accordance with the suggestion of Higasi governing the positive solvent effect⁷.

The dipole moment values determined by earlier workers for the amines in question in benzene besides being higher are not in fair agreement. Therefore the measurement for these amines in benzene have been carried out by the methods due to Halverstadt and Kumler as well as by the method of Palit.

The most probable value for the dipole moment of Iso-amyl amine is observed to be 1.44 D. In this case too we observe that the literature value 1.53 D for this compound appears to be higher.

The dipole moment values in dioxan for all the three amines as shown in table 6 are Contribution to the literature. The data of table 6 further illuminate that the results obtained by Palit equation is comparable and much convincing.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. R. C. Kapoor, Head, Department of Chemistry, for providing necessary facilities. One of us (P. R. T.) is grateful to C. S. I. R., New Delhi for awarding a senior research fellowship.

References

1. G. HEDESTRAND., *Z. Physik. Chem.* 1929, **B2**, 428.
2. F. E. HOECKER., *J. Chem. Phys.* 1936, **4**, 431.
3. I. F. HALVERSTADT and W. D. KUMLER., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 2988.
4. R. J. W. LEFEVRE and H. VINE., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1805.
5. A. N. SRIVASTAVA and P. R. TALESARA., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 359.
6. D. V. G. L. N. RAO., *Indian J. Phys.* 1950, **33**, 51.
7. B. KRISHNA and A. N. SRIVASTAVA., *Austral J. Chem.* 1966, **19**, 1847.